



Supplementary Fig. 1: Stacked area plots of relative abundance of indicator species and other calcareous and agglutinated species by locality. Shaded area represents BZ samples.



Supplementary Fig. 2: Stacked area plots of relative abundance of morphotypes by locality. Shaded area represents BZ samples.



Supplementary Fig 3: Boxplots of nonBZ samples by region.